

MEDICAL SCIENCES

SKIN MANIFESTATIONS IN PREGNANCY

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Abstract

Pregnancy is a physiological state that induces skin manifestations. The presence of the fetus in the womb produces responses in the maternal body outside the physiological limits and consequently leads to the appearance of some pathological manifestations. Their rational treatment requires specifying the etiology. Gestationes Pemphigoid is a rare, intensely itchy skin condition that occurs only in association with pregnancy. It appears in the second or third trimester of pregnancy. The Polymorphous Eruption of pregnancy usually affects first pregnancy in the third trimester or immediately postpartum. About the Cholestasis Intrahepatic of pregnancy it has a prevalence of 1%, and develops in genetically predisposed people.

Keywords: Pregnancy, transformations, skin manifestations, Gestationes Pemphigoid, Polymorphous Eruption, Cholestasis Intrahepatic.

Dermatoses induced by pregnancy are rare conditions, generally benign, with the exception of Herpetiform Impetigo. They require an efficient non-aggressive treatment resulting from the collaboration of two involved clinicians, a dermatologist and a gynecologist. These pathological manifestations appear, with varying degrees of severity, they appear only during pregnancy, disappear after the expulsion of the product of conception and have the possibility of reappearing with a new pregnancy. Clasification of dermatoses: prurigo gravida, acute pruritus gravida, papular dermatosis of pregnancy, pruritic folliculitis of pregnancy, bullous pemphigoid, impetigo herpetiform.

Gestationis pemphigoid is a rare and intensely pruritic autoimmune disease of the skin in pregnancy. The incidence is approximately 1 in 60.000 pregnancies, and the disease represents a worldwide distribution. In this pathology, the first immune response is located in the placenta. Circulating IgG antibodies are developed that react with the amniotic epithelium of the placental

tissues. The autoimmune response consists in the deposition of immune complexes, the activation of complement, the consecutive chemoattraction of eosinophils and degranulation, leading to tissue damage and the appearance of skin manifestations.[142] In the same way, this pathology exacerbates after the administration of postpartum oral contraceptives, so we can observe the impact of sexual hormones in the pathogenesis of this pathology. Initially, the disease presents itchy urticarial papules and annular plaques, followed by vesicles, large bubbles on an erythematous background. The most common place of eruption is periumbilical area. In 90% it spreads to the rest of the abdomen, sometimes even to the thighs, arms. These manifestations disappear in the first months after birth, but may return in next pregnancies.[145]The diagnosis is based on the clinical evaluation, histological findings, direct immunofluorescence. Direct immunofluorescence shows a linear arrangement of the complement IgG and C3 in the antigenic area of the basement membrane. Treatment with oral corticosteroids is sufficient.[143]

Figura 1. Periumbilical rash in PG.

PEP(The Polymorphic Rash of Pregnancy) is a benign, self-limiting inflammatory disorder that affects primigravida in the third trimester. The theory suggests

an overdistension. The morphology changes, while the disease progresses, developing polymorphic characteristics, such as papulovesicles, erythema.[144]

Figura 2. Pruritic urticarial rashes in PEP.

The treatment is symptomatic. We use topical corticosteroids with or without antihistamines, but in severe cases a short treatment with systemic corticosteroids may be necessary.[146] This pathology is not associated with risks for the newborn. The maternal prognosis is excellent in most cases. In addition, not all

antihistamines are used during pregnancy; cetirizine, loratidine should be preferred.[147]

Intrahepatic Cholestasis of pregnancy (ICP), known as pruritus gravidarum, is a liver disease characterized by severe itching and secondary skin lesions in the third trimester of pregnancy. It occurs in genetically predisposed people.[148]

Figura 3 .Excoriations, scratches and nodules in the ICP.

The treatment need to decrease the level of serum bile acid and alleviate itching. Ursodeoxycholic acid can be used to reduce the severity of itching and has been shown to give a favorable result for pregnancy. UVB phototherapy can be used in refractory cases.[149,150].

This pathology is correlated with fetal risks, the most frequent being premature birth (20-60%), followed by intrapartum fetal distress (20-30%) and stillbirth (2%). In this prolonged pathology, cholestasis can cause vitamin K deficiency and coagulopathy of patients and children. Thus, these risks make it necessary to closely monitor them during and after birth.[151]

A correct diagnosis of these pregnancy-induced dermatoses is very important in terms of fetal and maternal prognosis. These conditions must be seen as diseases of the whole body, requiring a series of general, hygienic-dietetic measures and pregnancy supervision.

References

1. Pfaltz K, Mertz K, Rose C, Scheidegger P, Pfaltz M, Kempf W. Sitaru C, Powell J, Brocker EB, Wojnarowska F, Zillikens D. Immunoblotting and enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay for the diagnosis of pemphigoid gestationis, *Obstet Gynecol.* 2014, p. 116
2. Boudaya S, Turki H, Meziou TJ, Marrekchi S, Bouassida S, Zahaf A. Pemphigoid gestationis: a study of 15 cases, *J Gynecol Obstet Biol Reprod (Paris).* 2013, p. 26
3. Brites D. Intrahepatic cholestasis of pregnancy: changes in maternal-fetal bile acid balance and improvement by ursodeoxycholic acid, *Ann Hepatol.* 2012, p. 159-145. Cobo MF, Santi CG, Maruta CW, Aoki V. Pemphigoid gestationis: clinical and laboratory evaluation, *Clinics (Sao Paulo).* 2019, p. 79

4. Lewis V. Skin problems in pregnancy, *Medicine*. 2014, p. 60
5. Nanda A, Al-Saeed K, Dvorak R, Al-Muzairai I, Al-Sabah H, Al-Arbash M, Ohel I, Levy A, Silbestein T., et al Pregnancy outcome of patients with plaques and pruritic urticarial papules of pregnancy, *J Maternal Fetal Neonatal Med*. 2016, p. 37-48. Terra JB, Jonkman MF. Diagnostic image. A pregnant female with blisters, *Ned Tijdschr Geneesk*. 2019, p. 130
6. Solberg SM, Tolaas E, Sviland L. A pregnant woman with itching rash, *Tidsskr Nor Laegeforen*. 2018, p. 85-150. Szepetiuk G, Mélotte C, Piérard-Franchimont C, Quatresooz P, Piérard GE. How I explore... pruritus in a pregnant woman, *Rev Med Liege*. 2017, p. 143
7. Tarocchi S, Carli P. Polymorphic eruption of pregnancy, *International Journal of Dermatology*. 2018, p. 69

IMMUNE ANEMIAS AND THROMBOCYTOPENIAS IN NON-HODGKIN'S LYMPHOMAS

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Abstract

Non-Hodgkin lymphomas (NHL) are the most common hematological malignancies, the incidence of which has shown a significant increase in rates over the year, worldwide, as well as in the Republic of Moldova. [1] The association of immune complications in patients with NHL is common, which can be appreciated shortly before or during the manifestation of the malignant lymphoma. [2, 3] On the basis of a database of 64 NHLs patients registered at the Oncological Institute, Chisinau, Republic of Moldova, a study was done to examine the clinical, and evolutionary particularities of immune anemias and thrombocytopenias in NHL. Immune hemolytic anemia (IHA) and immune thrombocytopenia (IT) are the most common immune complications and are more commonly in indolent NHL, advanced stages, nodal and spleen NHL onset, female gender. NHLs were most frequently associated with an immune comorbidity, and much less often concomitant immune comorbidities were appreciated.

Keywords: lymphoma, immune hemolytic anemia, immune thrombocytopenia.

Introduction

The association of immune complications in patients with NHL is common, which can be appreciated shortly before or during the manifestation of the malignant lymphoma. [2, 3] In some cases, the development of the immune component can be induced by the antineoplastic therapy. [4] It still remains an enigma the synthesis of antibodies after finishing the specific chemotherapy treatment applied to patients with NHL. [5] Based on the above, at the new patient with NHL can be not only the characteristic manifestations of NHL, but the association of immune hemolytic anemia manifested by anemic and hemolytic syndromes, immune thrombocytopenia represented by the hemorrhagic syndrome. Most immune comorbidities are associated with B-cell NHL, because B lymphocytes have a well-established role in the pathogenesis of immune disease, representing a source of erroneous synthesis of antibodies against one's own cells. [6, 7]

IHA is the most common immune complication recognized in patients with NHL, followed by Evans syndrome, erythroblastopenia, and IT. [8] Secondary IHA mainly develops against the background of lymphoproliferative diseases and autoimmune diseases, constituting approximately 50% of cases. [9] Hu et al's retrospective analysis of 4880 patients with NHL assessed IHA in 766 (15.7%) patients. In the case of patients with T-cell NHL, secondary IHA was appreciated in 57.14% of cases. [10]

Evans syndrome is more commonly diagnosed in patients aged 50-60 years, and in 27-50% of cases it is secondary to lymphoproliferative diseases and SLE. [11, 14] Hematological malignancies are the main factors with an impact on the development of Evans syndrome and its prognosis. [12, 13]

IT secondary to NHL, is a rare disease [15] and is diagnosed with a much lower frequency compared to IHA, being evaluated in only up to 1.8% of cases. [16, 17] The immune reaction underlying the development of secondary IT is complex, consisting of several consecutive stages in which B lymphocytes, T lymphocytes, NK, macrophages, cytokines participate.

Materials and methods

The study included 64 new patients with NHL, associated with immune comorbidities, treated in the Oncological Institute, Republic of Moldova, during the years 2020-2021. The average age of the patients is 62.3±3 years (33-76 years). The immune component developed more frequently in women - 44 (69%), compared to men - 20 (31%). The distribution of patients with NHL and autoimmune component according to the type of NHL demonstrated a more frequent association of immune disease in the case of the development of indolent NHL 34 (58%) patients as opposed to the development of aggressive NHL 30 (42%) patients. IHA and IT were confirmed by researching blood count, unconjugated bilirubin level, LDH, as well as response to immunosuppressive treatment. The database